

Entrepreneurship Education On Entrepreneurial Intentions Of Electrical And Electronics Education Students, Mediation Of Attitudes, Subjective Norms And Perceived Behavioural Control

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intentions of electrical and electronics education students, mediation of attitudes, subjective norms and perceived behavioural control. This study used correlational research design. Three hypotheses were tested in this study. The population consisted of 126 electrical and electronics education students who participated in entrepreneurship education in universities in Southeastern Nigeria. A structured questionnaire made up of 26 items divided into five sub-scales, adapted from already validated and published scales, was used in this study. The adapted scale had a Cronbach Alpha indexes of 0.94, 0.90, 0.77, 0.89, and 0.94 for each cluster respectively, indicating that the instrument was reliable for measuring the constructs. The adapted instrument was subjected to confirmatory factor analysis to ensure that the instrument achieve a good model fit index and thereafter administered to the respondents. On the online data collection approach, 114 responses were collected and analysed using mediation analysis of partial least square structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM). It was found from the study that entrepreneurship education positively correlates with entrepreneurial intentions of students. However, the findings of this showed that attitudes towards behaviour did not mediate the effects of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intentions of students, whereas, subjective Norms and perceived behavioural control had negative mediation effects on the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intentions of students. In conclusion, the researchers state that Nigerian government should create an entrepreneurship-friendly environment, where people would find it easy to start and run a successful business. The researchers therefore recommend that educational bodies should emphasize more on the role of attitudes towards behaviour, subjective norms and perceived behavioural control on students' entrepreneurial intentions.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship Education, Entrepreneurial Intentions, Electrical and Electronics Education Students, Attitudes, Subjective Norms, Perceived Behavioural Control

INTRODUCTION

Offorman, (2015) defined entrepreneurship education as a formal and structured instruction that convey entrepreneurial knowledge which develops students' awareness relating to opportunity recognition and creation of new ventures. It inculcates in students the ability to seek information and advice; make decision; plan ones' time and energy and carryout the responsibilities that are involved in venture creation processes. Entrepreneurship education has been grouped into: education "about", "for" "through" and "in" entrepreneurship education according to Sirelkhatim and Ganji (2015). The "about" type of entrepreneurship education teaches students entrepreneurial concept, its importance and the relevant theories. It is theoretical in nature and thus equips students with entrepreneurial knowledge for firm creation. The "for" type of entrepreneurship education prepare students to become entrepreneurs. It allows students to be engaged in activities that equip them with practical entrepreneurial skills and competencies needed for entrepreneurial career. The "through" type of entrepreneurship education has some similarities with that of "for" type of entrepreneurship education in terms of contents and teaching approaches except that the "through" type of entrepreneurship education allows actual practice of entrepreneurial activities in real-life. It allows students to have an experience of what it means to be an entrepreneur in real-life instead of pretending to be one. The "in" type of entrepreneurship education (also called the "embedded" type) integrates entrepreneurship education into non-business disciplines so that students can acquire certain entrepreneurial skills relevant to their field of interest.

Meanwhile, entrepreneurship education requires effective teaching methods that can impart the techniques of applying contextual learning and real-life experiences to enhance entrepreneurial activities of students (Farny *et al.*, 2016; Potishuk and Kratzer, 2017). Nwankwo and Nnajiolor (2021) opined that course contents adapted for entrepreneurship education in Nigerian university is effective in enhancing students' understanding of entrepreneurial concepts and also adequate in preparing Nigerian graduates for firm creation. The authors further stated that the problem associated with entrepreneurship education in Nigeria is the teaching methods used to teach entrepreneurship education, because the main elements of entrepreneurship education such as exposure to field trips, exposure to small/medium scale enterprises and interaction with successful entrepreneurs were not given adequate attention during teaching and learning.

In consideration to the above discussion, many researchers have advocated that appropriate teaching techniques that could allow students obtain appropriate information about business and its practices should be applied to teach entrepreneurship courses in the universities so that the students can adopt the best procedures in establishing business ventures (Cui, Sun and Bell, 2019; Taiwo and Joseph, 2020). In support of the above, Mamman *et al.* (2018) stated that entrepreneurship education contents, methods and activities that support firm creation, development of knowledge, competency and experience make it desirable and feasible for students to initiate and follow all the processes involved in creating entrepreneurial ventures. From the above discussion, it can be deduced that students who participate in an organised entrepreneurship education will likely compete favorably with others in the labour market and shall perform better than others in terms of implementation of entrepreneurial plans. Therefore, entrepreneurship education conveys more advantageous outcomes in enhancing education, innovations and economic wellbeing of individuals (Mendonca *et al.*, 2022).

Several studies have been done by many researchers on entrepreneurship education, and most of the studies affirmed that entrepreneurship education facilitates students' entrepreneurial behaviour (Cui and Bell, 2022; Igwe, Okolie, and Nwokoro, 2021; Tomy and Pardede, 2018). Another study done by Wardana *et al.* (2020) stated that entrepreneurship education trains students on how to handle entrepreneurial task which includes analyzing business feasibilities, writing business plan and the processes of executing the business plan. Otache *et al.* (2019) also stated that entrepreneurship education encourages students to be self-employed. These are the advantages of entrepreneurship education which are very important especially on how to start up and manage businesses. It also provides job opportunities, shaping the innate capabilities in creating business, inculcates in the mentality of hard work and empowers students with innovative skills in creating business (Oluka and Ideh, 2021). More also,

Dogan (2015) stated that entrepreneurship education has the capacity to produce successful entrepreneurs and hereby recommend that entrepreneurship education should be properly implemented in tertiary institutions to enhance entrepreneurship. Shodipe and Ohanu (2020) stated that entrepreneurship education deals with opportunity recognition of new business venture and thereby encourage graduates to engage in it for profit making. Mamabolo, Kerrin, and Kele (2017) stated that entrepreneurship education encourages human capital investment which produces skills and knowledge, self-confidence and motivation for entrepreneurial venture. Again, Bello *et al.* (2018) stated that entrepreneurship education provides the practical skills and knowledge and information about the latest trends in the world. It also reveals societal problems and encourages the desires to startup businesses. Entrepreneurship education contributes towards community development in terms of changing behaviour and pattern of doing things for societal and environmental needs. Likewise, Aboobaker and Renjini (2020) posited that entrepreneurship education prepares students with theoretical foundations of entrepreneurship, practical and practices of entrepreneurship, techniques of entrepreneurship and its relationship in entrepreneurial ventures. Otache, Edopkolor and Kadiri (2022) stated that entrepreneurship education develops skills such as opportunity recognition, exploitation, initiative and risk-taking, business conception and development, innovation, creativity, tolerance for uncertainty and self-confidence on students. Therefore, entrepreneurship education can help students to develop self-confidence in discovering and starting up entrepreneurial ventures for financial and physical benefits even in electrical and electronics.

In electrical and electronics, there are trained teachers who serve as craftsmen (proficiently skilled personnel) to inculcate practical skills of electrical and electronics to students. The programme trains students to acquire technical literacy and numeracy, adaptability and flexibility, communication, problem-solving and critical thinking, collaboration and teamwork, innovation and creativity, and management and leadership skills that are required for entrepreneurial activities. The teachers also train students to meet up with the expectation of the society in terms of norms, morals and values needed for the entrepreneurial behaviour, economic growth and development. Skills in both industrial and rural electrification, inspection, testing and maintenance of electrical machines (motors and generators) and electrical/electronic devices were taught to electrical and electronics education students to offer them greater entrepreneurial opportunities in the field of electrical and electronics (Shodipe and Ohanu, 2020). Therefore, electrical and electronics education programme has the capacity to enhance graduate's entrepreneurial activities for firm creation in electrical and electronics.

Consequently, it can be perceived that the opinions and attitudes of reference groups such as relatives and peers could have influence on students' choice of career, and the ability of the student to take action to actualise the desired career, influence entrepreneurial activities of such students. Some of the students can choose entrepreneurial career based on the education received, whereas others may choose entrepreneurial career based on interest. Some are influenced by parents, peers and friends (Nwobu, Faboyede and Oyewo, 2015;) and since experience is one of the factors that influence students' entrepreneurial intention, it is presumed in this study that educational experiences (entrepreneurship education) may have influence on students' entrepreneurial intention.

Notwithstanding, the relationship of entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intention does not just occur without certain intervening variables. In other words, entrepreneurial education will have influence on some certain variables, which will in turn have influence on entrepreneurial intention of such students. In this study, such variables that are in-between the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intentions of students are considered as mediator variables. Mediator variables are behavioral, biological, psychological, or social constructs that transmit the effect of one variable to another variable. From the theory of planned behaviour (TPB – Ajzen, 1991), intention is a function of one's attitude (ATB), subjective norm (SN) and perceived behavioural control (PBC) which are considered as antecedents to behavioural intention, and therefore the presumed mediating variables in this study.

Attitude towards behaviour (ATB) refers to the degree to which students have favourable and unfavourable evaluation of a particular behaviour (Rohit, 2016). It can also be seen as students'

assessment of the likely consequences or outcome of a given behaviour. In the context of this study, attitude toward entrepreneurship reflects the degree to which electrical and electronics education students think positively or negatively about being an entrepreneur. Therefore, positive attitude towards entrepreneurial behaviour could lead to stronger intention for firm creation. It is clear that students might have a positive, negative, or neutral attitude about a given behaviour. If the attitude of students becomes more positive towards entrepreneurial activities, their intentions to perform entrepreneurial behaviour will increase. Meanwhile, attitude towards behaviour refers to the degree to which a student holds a positive or negative personal valuation about being an entrepreneur (Ozaralli and Rivenburgh, 2016). For example, Lee-Ross (2017) stated that attitude towards behaviour is dominant in determining one's success or failure to overcome challenges when faced with equivocal situations in life. Others, such as Aragon-Sanchez *et al.* (2017) stated that students with more positive attitude towards a given situation (entrepreneurial intention) are more likely to succeed in entrepreneurial ventures. Likewise, Amofah and Saladrigues (2022) stated that attitude toward entrepreneurial behaviour was the most important determinant of intention to become self-employed and attitude influences personality of the respondents. Several authors (Aragon-Sanchez *et al.*, 2017; Ogbonna, 2021) have established the significant relationship between attitude towards behaviour and entrepreneurial intentions in different circumstances. The above authors agreed that attitude towards behaviour could enhance entrepreneurial intentions of students in other fields of study.

Additionally, subjective norms (SN) refer to the students' perception of social pressure to perform or not to perform a particular behaviour (Ahmed *et al.*, 2020). Subjective norm means students' perception of the opinions of social reference groups (such as family and friends) about whether or not they should start a business (Pham *et al.*, 2022). In this study, it is the assessment of electrical and electronics education students on how people in their environment feel about their intent, plan, or decision to venture into business. It is also the importance other people place on them towards performing an entrepreneurial behaviour. In other words, it can be seen as the degree to which a student perceives another people's opinion to engage in entrepreneurial behaviour. It can therefore be deduced that an increase in subjective norm of students, could influence their intentions to perform entrepreneurial behaviour. It can also be perceived as a social pressure to perform or not to perform an entrepreneurial behaviour. Although, Aragon-Sanchez *et al.* (2017) define subjective norm as how a student would behave in a particular setting in respect to the opinion of the reference groups like family members, friends and colleagues. Entrepreneurship is connected with many risks and challenges that may not be easily adopted by students on graduation, but the pressure that may come from friends or peer groups can pressurize students to execute a given task (Nwigwe, 2021). This implies that entrepreneurship is associated with numerous challenges and risks that may not be easily welcomed in the lifestyle of a student. Thus, the pressure that may emanate from family members or the generality of society may enforce a student to execute specific tasks or not.

Another antecedent to intention is perceived behavioural control (PBC) of students. This is an individual perception of the ease or difficulty of becoming an entrepreneur. Perceived behavioural control could be seen in this context as the control beliefs of electrical and electronics education students concerning entrepreneurial behaviour. It is also be perceived as students' sense of capacity regarding the fulfillment of firm-creation. PBC would include not only students' feeling of being able, but also the perception about controllability of the behaviour (Linan and Chen, 2009). Perceived behavioural control can be defined as students perceived available factors that may facilitate or hinder the performance of a given behaviour (George and Ernest, 2017). This involves students' perception of their ability that they can perform entrepreneurial behaviour, events or activities pertaining to business career. To clarify the above assertion, it can be said that perceived behavioural control is behaviour or goal specific.

Furthermore, perception of students on entrepreneurial activities varies based on environmental circumstances and processes of entrepreneurial activities involved. For example, the theory of planned behaviour proposed that students are much more likely to act entrepreneurially when they feel that they can act on entrepreneurial activities successfully. This is because perceived behavioural control depicts

the perception of students' ability to influence the outcome of behaviour (Hsiao and Tang, 2013). This proves that perceived behavioural control can affect the level of aspiration of students for entrepreneurship. In the entrepreneurship perspective, perceived behavioural control simply refers to how challenging or easy it is for a student to start up a particular business, manage it and succeed in that business ventures (Nwigwe, 2021). In overall, these three antecedents to behavioural intention can facilitate or impede the performance of electrical and electronics education students towards entrepreneurial activities. Hence, this study.

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested in this study at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Attitude towards behaviour will not significantly mediate the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intentions of electrical and electronics education students in Universities in Southeastern Nigeria
2. Subjective norms will not significantly mediate the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intentions of electrical and electronics education students in Universities in Southeastern Nigeria
3. Perceived behavioural control will not significantly mediate the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intentions of electrical and electronics education students in Universities in Southeastern Nigeria.

METHOD

This study used correlational research design. A correlational research design is a quantitative research approach that investigates relationships between variables without the researchers controlling or manipulating any of the variables. It aims to ascertain the relationships/correlations between variables of interest in the naturalistic setting (Lau, 2017). This study was carried out in Southeastern part of Nigeria. Southeastern Nigeria is one of the six geopolitical zones in Nigeria that represents both the geographical and political region of the country. The Southeast geopolitical zone of Nigeria is made up of 5 states, namely, Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo with 85 Local Government Areas (L. G. A). The region has a population of over 36 million people (18% of the total population of Nigeria) dwelling in the over 10 commercial cities and large towns in the area. 25 accredited Universities exist in this region and 5 of the Universities offer electrical and electronics education. 126 electrical and electronics education students completed entrepreneurship education course in 2023/2024 academic session and they all participated in the study. The choice of this population was because, these students were expected to be self-reliance on graduation and entrepreneurship education plays a vital role in future career decisions and self-reliance.

Furthermore, the instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled Entrepreneurship Education and Entrepreneurial Intentions Instrument (EEEEI) which was adapted from already validated and published scales. The instrument comprised 26 items and the adapted scale had a Cronbach Alpha indexes of 0.94, 0.90, 0.77, 0.89, and 0.94 for each cluster respectively, indicating that the instrument was reliable for measuring the constructs. The adapted instrument was subjected to confirmatory factor analysis to ensure that the instrument achieve a good model fit index. To enable the researchers to test the hypotheses, all the adapted measurement scales were subjected to confirmatory factor (CFA) to ensure that the current data fit well. Thus, the researchers used the following model fit indices: Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Incremental Fit Index (IFI) and Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) ≥ 0.90 ; Normed Chi-Square (χ^2/df) ≤ 3.0 ; standardized root mean squared residual (SRMR) ≤ 0.08 and root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) ≤ 0.06 (Hair et al., 2010; Hu & Bentler, 1999). The standardized results of the initial CFA with all the variables and their item statements are shown below.

The results of the initial seven-factor CFA model showed good model fit as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Model Fit Measures

Measure	Estimate	Threshold	Interpretation
CMIN	904.919	--	--
DF	413.000	--	--
CMIN/DF	2.191	Between 1 and 3	Excellent
CFI	0.822	>0.95	Acceptable
IFI	0.802	>0.90	Acceptable
TLI	0.800	>0.90	Acceptable
SRMR	0.076	<0.08	Excellent
RMSEA	0.089	<0.06	Acceptable

Although the values of CFI, IFI and TLI are not up to the recommended 0.90, Kline (2015) recommended that model fit measures with moderate values above 0.80 can be considered when the CFA model contains many variables.

Thus, the researchers proceeded with the validity and reliability checks for the model. To establish the validity and reliability of the measurement scales, the following indices were used: composite reliability (CR) ≥ 0.60 and Cronbach's alpha (α) reliability ≥ 0.70 . The discriminant validity (DV) values for all the measurement scales were obtained by the square root of the average variance extracted (AVE), (Hair et al., 2010; Hu & Bentler, 1999).

Table 2: Reliability and Validity Results

Variables	CR	Cronbach's Alpha	AVE	DV
Entrepreneurship Education	0.838	0.867	0.511	0.715
Attitude Towards Behaviour	0.910	0.928	0.561	0.749
Subjective Norms	0.847	0.910	0.649	0.805
Perceived Behavioural Control	0.888	0.921	0.665	0.815
Entrepreneurial Intentions	0.884	0.891	0.554	0.744

Having achieved the validity and reliability measures for all variables in the study, the researchers followed Collier's (2020) recommendations to use the maximum Likelihood Estimate in AMOS to calculate the normality assumptions of the data for the current study. The absolute value of skewness 1.0 or less shows that the data is normally distributed. Collier (2020) noted that for kurtosis, the range is -10 to +10 for normally distributed data when calculated using AMOS. Also, values of the critical ratio for the skewness as shown in Table 3 below do not exceed ± 8.0 . Thus, the data sample is considered normally distributed.

Table 3: Assessment of Normality

Variable	min	max	skew	c.r.	kurtosis	c.r.
EI3	1.000	5.000	-0.307	-1.340	-1.488	-3.244
EE5	1.000	5.000	-1.299	-5.662	2.563	5.587

Variable	min	max	skew	c.r.	kurtosis	c.r.
EI6	1.000	5.000	-.752	-3.279	-.915	-1.993
ATB4	1.000	5.000	-1.112	-4.848	.448	.977
ATB3	1.000	5.000	-1.285	-5.602	.904	1.969
ATB2	1.000	5.000	-1.210	-5.273	.682	1.485
ATB1	1.000	5.000	-1.222	-5.328	.574	1.251
PBC1	1.000	5.000	-1.053	-4.588	.104	.227
PBC3	1.000	5.000	-1.051	-4.583	.314	.685
PBC4	1.000	5.000	-1.224	-5.335	.615	1.339
PBC5	1.000	5.000	-1.122	-4.893	.347	.756
SN3	2.000	5.000	-.934	-4.072	-.245	-.534
SN2	1.000	5.000	-1.145	-4.993	.471	1.027
SN1	1.000	5.000	-.949	-4.138	-.155	-.338
EI5	1.000	5.000	-.667	-2.908	-1.099	-2.394
EI4	1.000	5.000	-.524	-2.286	-1.293	-2.818
EI2	1.000	5.000	-.810	-3.532	-.561	-1.223
EI1	1.000	5.000	-.601	-2.619	-1.118	-2.437
EE1	1.000	5.000	-1.539	-6.707	3.956	8.621
EE3	1.000	5.000	-1.396	-6.086	3.604	7.856
EE4	2.000	5.000	-.890	-3.880	.676	1.473
EE6	1.000	5.000	-1.053	-4.588	1.336	2.912
Multivariate					75.243	31.423

For Internal consistency, Cronbach alpha test was used which were presented in the table 2 above. Each construct value is more than the required value of 0.7, therefore, there is a presence of internal consistency in the model. The convergent validity was determined using *average variance extracted (AVE)* as shown in table 2 above in which the values are all greater than 0.5. The examination presents that convergent validity is present and appropriate in the model. The Composite reliability as presented in table 2 which the values are all greater than the required value of 0.7. Thus, the model has composite reliability. There is also an existence of discriminant validity in the model as shown in table 2. As all the criteria for reliability and validity are being met, the model was reliable and valid. It indicates that the instrument was reliable and was used to measure the constructs under investigation. Thereafter the instrument was administered to all electrical and electronics education students in universities in Southeastern Nigeria. On the online data collection approach, 114 responses were collected. Meanwhile, the researchers promised to maintain confidentiality of data collected. Additionally, the online form also sought students' consent before they filled the Google form. Students' university, email addresses and level of study assisted the researchers to ascertain the level of completion of the instrument, track and monitor their responses to avoid double completion and unwanted responses. The motive was to ensure 100% completion rate of the instrument by students. However, out of 126 students, 114 completed the instrument and 12 students did not respond, making a total of 90.5% completion rate. The students' responses on the instrument were obtained from the online Google form in CSV format which was converted or downloaded into excel spreadsheet. From excel spreadsheet it was converted to IBM SPSS version 24 and then to SPSS Amos version 24 for data analysis.

Hypotheses Testing

In testing hypotheses, Path Analysis in AMOS 24.0 was employed and all estimates were calculated using the maximum likelihood with bootstrapping (2000 resampling at 95% confidence intervals). The path

model included entrepreneurship education (independent variable), attitude towards behaviour, subjective norm and perceived behavioural control (mediator variables), entrepreneurial intention (dependent variable), In testing the mediation effects, the researchers employed the user-defined estimands functions in AMOS following recommendations (Hayes, 2017). Thus, a full structural path model was assessed (e.g., Hooper et al., 2008) as shown below

Fig 1. Picture Showing Structural Path Model Fit Measures.

Table 4: Structural Path Model Fit Measures

Measure	Estimate	Threshold	Interpretation
CMIN	19.458	--	--
DF	9.000	--	--
CMIN/DF	2.162	Between 1 and 3	Excellent
CFI	0.990	>.90	Excellent
IFI	0.990	>.90	Excellent
TLI	0.971	>.90	Excellent

SRMR	0.022	<0.08	Excellent
RMSEA	0.087	<0.06	Acceptable

Table5: User-defined estimands: (Mediation Results)

Relationships	Estimates	Lower Bound	Upper Bound	P
Entrep → ATB → Intentions	.002	-.230	.162	.966
Entrep → SN → Intentions	-.245	-.547	-.078	.006
Entrep → PBC → Intentions	-.108	-.315	.134	.305

Note: Entrep. = Entrepreneurship Education, ATB = Attitude towards behaviour, SN = Subject norms and PBC = Perceived behavioural control.

1. The mediation result ($\beta = 0.00, P = .97$) as shown in the Table 5 above revealed that attitudes towards behaviour did not mediate the effects of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intentions of electrical and electronics education students. Thus, Hypothesis 1 was rejected. It implies that attitudes towards behaviour did not mediate the effects of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intentions of students.
2. The mediation result ($\beta = -0.25, P = .01$) as shown in the Table 5 above revealed that subjective Norms had a negative mediation effect on the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intentions of electrical and electronics education students. Thus, Hypothesis 2 was rejected. This implies that subjective Norms had a negative mediation effect on the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intentions of students.
3. The mediation result ($\beta = -0.11, P = .31$) as shown in the Table 5 above revealed that perceived behavioural control had negative mediation effect on the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intentions of electrical and electronics education students. Thus, Hypothesis 3 was rejected. It shows that perceived behavioural control negatively mediated the effects of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intentions of electrical and electronics education students.

DISCUSSION

In testing hypothesis 1 the finding stated that attitudes towards behaviour did not mediate the effects of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intentions of students. The above result implies that students' attitudes toward behaviour and their perceived ability to engage in entrepreneurial activities did not explain how entrepreneurship education affects their intentions to pursue entrepreneurship. As hypothesized, the mediating effect of attitude towards behaviour on the relationship between perceived entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intentions was not confirmed. It is clear that attitude towards behaviour did not mediate the relationship between perceived entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intentions of students. In practical terms, the results show that attitude towards behaviour absorbs the effects of perceived entrepreneurship education and did not transfer the effects to entrepreneurial intentions of students. In other words, attitude towards behaviour could have helped to explain the influence of perceived entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intentions of students but it did not show any relationship between the variable of investigation. These finding is in agreement with the findings of the past related studies on the impact of attitude towards behaviour on entrepreneurial intentions of students (Kautonen et al., 2015; Rauch and Hulsink, 2015). Furthermore, this finding underscores the importance of attitude towards behaviour among the constructs of the TPB in the

entrepreneurial process. Despite this significant finding as stated, the fact that this study has reported no mediation effects suggests that there may be other factors that explain the influence of perceived entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intentions other than attitude towards behaviour. For example, self-confidence is a potential mediator variable in the relationship between perceived entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intentions. Self-confidence is required for one to establish a business venture and research evidence has demonstrated that perceived entrepreneurship education is capable of instilling self-confidence into the students (Mamun et al., 2015). Likewise, research has shown that self-confidence is positively linked to entrepreneurial intentions of students (Margahana and Negara, 2019). This suggests that self-confidence could help explain the effects of perceived entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intentions of students

Secondly, in hypothesis 2 testing, subjective Norms had a negative mediation effect on the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intentions of students. It is clear from this study that subjective norms (students' perceptions of social expectations or pressures from significant people around them) diminished the positive impact of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intentions of students. It could also mean that even if students received entrepreneurship education and they perceive social disapproval or lack of support from their peers, family, or community, their likelihood to engage in entrepreneurship decreased. This negative mediation suggests that social pressures can counteract the benefits of entrepreneurship education by reducing students' motivation or confidence to pursue entrepreneurial careers. Consequently, these findings highlight the complexity of the factors influencing entrepreneurial intentions. While entrepreneurship education is crucial, social expectations (subjective norms) can undermine its positive effects, and students' attitudes or perceived capabilities do not play a negative significant mediating role in this context. This underscores the importance of addressing social pressures and expectations when designing entrepreneurship education programs to fully support students' entrepreneurial aspirations. To support the above finding, several analyses revealed that subjective norms had a positive correlation but no statistical significant relationship with students' entrepreneurial intentions and thus did not mediate the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intentions of students. Similarly, other findings have been reported by some past related studies concerning the mediating roles of variables on the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intentions of students (Autio et al., 2001; Fayolle and Gailly, 2015). The nonsignificant effect of subjective norms on the students' entrepreneurial intentions indicates that the opinions of individuals who are close to the students, for example, their relatives and friends could exert a significant negative influence on the entrepreneurial intentions of the students. While these results are consistent with other studies as stated above, a number of factors may be responsible for the nonsignificant impact of subjective norms on the students' entrepreneurial intentions in Nigeria. It may be as a result of the inadequate social support for entrepreneurship from relevant individuals and agencies. Moreover, it may be due to the existence of poor infrastructural facilities such as poor road network and unstable electricity supply and high cost of doing business, which make business environment unfriendly (Ikeji and Onuba, 2015; Ofili, 2014).

Lastly, the hypothesis 3 testing indicated that perceived behavioural control negatively mediated the effects of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intentions of students. Other analysis from previous studies revealed that perceived behavioural control had a positive relationship with the students' entrepreneurial intentions but in this study it had statistically negative relationship with the students' entrepreneurial intentions and thus negatively mediated the relationship between entrepreneurship education and students' entrepreneurial intentions. This finding has been reported by Linan and Chen (2009) and Passaro et al, (2018). The non-significant effect of perceived behavioural control on the students' entrepreneurial intentions shows that students' perceived easiness or difficulty to engage in entrepreneurship did not play a significant role in influencing their entrepreneurial intentions. While these results are consistent with other studies as stated above, a number of factors may be responsible for the nonsignificant impact of perceived behavioural control on the students' entrepreneurial intentions. It may be due to the prevalent weak entrepreneurial culture and mentality among Nigerians and the fact that

entrepreneurship is unattractive (Agri et al., 2018). It may also be due to the difficulty in accessing start-up capital and other resources required to start and run a successful business in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

It is therefore stated that attitude towards behaviour, subjective norms and perceived behavioural control did mediate the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intentions of electrical and electronics education students and were not strongly associated with entrepreneurial intentions of students. As stated earlier, these findings may be due to weak entrepreneurial culture, unattractiveness of entrepreneurship, high cost of doing business and inadequate social support for entrepreneurship from relevant individuals in Nigeria (Agri et al., 2018). This finding has raised a concern about the practicability of entrepreneurship in Nigeria. For example, in 2019, the World Bank stated that Nigeria scored least among the 190 Economies in the world in terms of ease of doing business (World Bank Group, 2019). Overall, the findings have implications for the Nigerian government in terms of the need to create an entrepreneurship-friendly environment, where people would find it easy to start and run a successful business.

RECOMMENDATION

1. Curriculum planners should emphasize more on the role of entrepreneurship towards the economic development on the society.
2. Ministry of Education should sensitize teachers in secondary schools to use practical teaching approach for effective instructional delivery.
3. Educational bodies should emphasize more of the role of attitudes towards behaviour, subjective norms and perceived behavioural control on students' entrepreneurial intentions.

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